

Misconceptions about Magnetic Maps

Kenneth J. Lohmann,^{1*} Nathan F. Putman,² Sönke Johnsen,³ Catherine M. F. Lohmann¹

1. Department of Biology, University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill, Chapel Hill, NC 27599
U.S.A.

2. LGL Ecological Research Associates, 4103 South Texas Avenue, Suite 211, Bryan, Texas 77802,
U.S.A.

3.) Department of Biology, Duke University, Durham, NC 27708, U.S.A.

* Corresponding author

Key words: Magnetoreception, magnetic maps, navigation, orientation

Paper should be cited as:

Lohmann, K. J., Putman, N. F., Johnsen, S., and C. M. F. Lohmann (2023) Misconceptions about magnetic maps. Preprint at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10052196>

Abstract

Evidence that animals use magnetic maps in navigation has come from magnetic displacement experiments, in which animals subjected to magnetic fields that exist at distant locations often respond as if they have been geographically displaced to the places where the fields exist. A recent paper argues that, if animals are poor at discriminating among similar magnetic fields, then many magnetic displacement studies are likely to involve magnetic fields that animals find ambiguous. Here we discuss evidence that, rather than being poor at such discrimination, many animals are quite sensitive to magnetic fields. Moreover, we show that the interpretation of previous magnetic displacement studies does not change even if, contrary to growing evidence, poor magnetic sensitivity is assumed. Additional common misconceptions about magnetic maps are discussed, including: (1) the erroneous idea that a magnetic field must represent to an animal a highly specific location; and (2) the idea that animals have geographic omniscience, including awareness of the magnetic field in places where they never go.

Main Text

Compelling evidence that animals use magnetic maps for navigation comes from magnetic displacement experiments in which animals are exposed to magnetic signatures (combinations of magnetic intensity, inclination, and occasionally declination) that exist in different geographic regions.¹⁻⁵ Diverse species respond to magnetic displacements as if they have been geographically displaced indicating that animals can use magnetic signatures to recognize geographic locations. In a recent paper, Schneider et al. (2023)⁶ argue that, if one assumes that animals have low sensitivity to variations in magnetic fields, then most magnetic signatures mark larger areas than researchers expect, and the same signatures might exist at multiple geographic locations. (Note that they use ‘sensitivity’ to mean the ability to discriminate between similar signals rather than the ability to detect a minimal signal). In their view, most magnetic signatures used previously are too ambiguous for animals to interpret. This opinion is puzzling, because, if true, then animals would presumably respond to these ‘ambiguous’ magnetic signatures with confusion and disorientation, rather than with directed movements that make sense in the context of their movement ecology, as is observed.

More specifically, the conclusions of Schneider et al. rest on three problematic assumptions. The first is their core assumption that animals have relatively low sensitivity to magnetic field differences. Schneider et al. base their analyses on what they say is “*the highest likely level of sensitivity to magnetic parameters in animals*”. Specifically, they assume that animals can detect differences of no less than 0.5 degrees of inclination and no less than 200 nT of intensity. In reality, the limits of magnetic sensitivity have not been established definitively in any animal, but numerous studies imply considerably higher sensitivity (Tables 1, 2).

For example, the assumption that 0.5 degrees of inclination represents the highest sensitivity possible is contradicted by two recent studies on birds. In the first, Wynn et al. (2020)⁷ demonstrate that small changes in inclination angle along a coastline are correlated with changes in nesting location of a seabird; the majority of birds that changed location did so when the inclination changed by 0.02 degrees or less. In the second, Wynn et al. (2022)⁸ present evidence that migratory songbirds use specific, presumably learned, inclination angle values to mark the endpoint of their return migrations. Because recovery sites of adult birds differed on average by about 5 km from the locations predicted by the inclination model, the results are consistent with an ability to detect inclination differences of at least 0.04 – 0.05 degrees. Similarly, an assumption of low magnetic sensitivity is difficult to reconcile with growing evidence that some animals, such as lobsters and newts, use magnetic maps over distances of only 4-37 km^{9,10}, or that subtle changes in local magnetic fields affect the distribution of nests in sea turtles.¹¹

The assumption that 200 nT represents the limits of intensity detection in animals is also inconsistent with many studies (Table 2). In two species of salmon, for example, remarkably small changes in field intensity have been correlated with changes in the proportion of fish that take one of two migratory routes around Vancouver Island to arrive at the Fraser River. For sockeye salmon, every ~31 nT increase is correlated with another 10% of the salmon shifting their migratory route north.¹² For pink salmon, every ~22 nT increase is correlated with another 10% of salmon shifting their migratory route north.¹² In sum, accumulating evidence suggests

that animal magnetic sensitivity is significantly higher, and possibly even a full order of magnitude better, than Schneider et al. assume, both for inclination (Table 1) and for intensity (Table 2).

A second assumption of Schneider et al. is that magnetic displacement experiments require animals to perceive magnetic signatures as precise locations. For example, they write “[It] is often a key requirement of interpretation that a virtually displaced individual will perceive its location to have changed to a specific location matching the new magnetic field conditions.” This is incorrect. Indeed, the term *regional magnetic field* has often been used to emphasize that animals may be responding to a large area and not to a specific location.^{1-3,13,15} Thus, contrary to what Schneider et al. contend, the idea that animals might interpret a magnetic field as an extended geographic area is already embedded in the literature.

Another assumption concerns the nature of magnetic maps. Implicit in their paper is the idea that a magnetic map precisely represents the world’s geography in the mind of the animal. Yet, we should not expect that an animal has such geographic omniscience. An animal is likely unaware that a magnetic signature located along its migratory route also exists hundreds of kilometers away. We should also not assume that animals use Cartesian maps or a mental map as people do. Some animal maps may just consist of simple rules for how to respond, such as “move south if the magnetic intensity exceeds that of the goal.”

In effect, Schneider et al. reimagine the world as it might appear to an animal with poor magnetic sensitivity and a global knowledge of geography, an approach that inverts what is known and unknown. We know from magnetic displacements how an animal responds to a specific magnetic field. We do not know the animal’s magnetic sensitivity or whether the animal is aware, as Schneider et al. worry, that a similar field exists far away in a place it never goes. We do not know how large an area the signature represents to the animal (a localized area or a broad region), or whether the animal imagines itself to be anywhere at all. In the absence of such information, we favor a more conservative approach in which experiments reveal responses of animals, and data, rather than assumptions, shape discussion.

Schneider et al. are correct that the precision of magnetic maps depends in part on the ability of animals to distinguish between similar magnetic fields, a point about which there is no contention¹⁵⁻¹⁸. We disagree, however, with their criticisms of four published papers and find that their analyses do not actually change the interpretation of these studies:

- 1.) Boström et al.¹⁹ exposed wheatears to two magnetically-simulated southward migrations, one along the standard route and one displaced to the west. Birds exposed to the displaced route stored more fat than birds exposed to the standard route. Schneider et al. contend that the birds must have been unsure whether they were east or west of the standard path. But even if that were so, the findings still imply that birds perceived the displaced route as distant from their normal route and then stored extra fat for a longer-than-normal flight. Thus, the interpretation of the results does not change.
- 2.) Fuxjager et al.¹⁴ exposed young sea turtles to four different magnetic signatures along their migratory route. Schneider et al. calculate that one particular magnetic signature extends partway across the ocean. They overlook, however, that this issue was discussed in the original paper, and that whether turtles encounter the field in multiple areas, or only in

one, is unknown. Schneider et al. also express doubt that turtles distinguished between two other magnetic signatures, primarily because the differences between the two approach the limit of sensitivity that they assume. But this is backwards: one determines the sensitivity of an animal by studying responses to signals; one does not determine responses using assumptions of sensitivity. Moreover, the totality of results - including magnetic displacements,^{1,3,14,15,20,21} ocean circulation models,²² and computer simulations²³ -- leaves little question that juvenile Atlantic loggerhead turtles use a magnetic map.

- 3.) Schneider et al. have misunderstood the study by Putman et al.²⁰ which demonstrated that turtles can distinguish between two magnetic fields that exist at the same latitude on opposite sides of the Atlantic. Schneider et al. argue that, if turtles have poor magnetic sensitivity, then they might have perceived the two magnetic fields as broad regions. Even assuming poor sensitivity, however, the turtles still distinguished between magnetic fields that exist on opposite sides of the ocean and responded in ways likely to facilitate their migration in each area. Schneider et al. argue that turtles do not detect longitude *per se* but overlook that Putman et al. arrived at the same conclusion. The primary finding was that a turtle's magnetic map functionally provides both north-south and east-west positional information.
- 4.) Schneider et al. also misunderstand the paper by Scanlan et al.²⁴ This study asked if a population of nonmigratory Atlantic salmon that had been translocated to inland waters several generations before possess the basics of a magnetic map. The fish responded similarly to magnetic displacements to both the Pacific and Atlantic Oceans, which suggested to Scanlan et al.²⁴ that salmon might use "*a simple rule that a stronger intensity and steeper inclination angle indicates northward displacement, whereas a weaker intensity and shallower inclination angle indicates a southward displacement.*" This interpretation does not rely on fish perceiving a magnetic displacement as a specific location, nor does it depend on whether the fish have high or low sensitivity to the magnetic field.

Schneider et al. also assert that some previous magnetic displacement studies contain errors in estimations of magnetic fields that exist at various locations. We note that Schneider et al. used the 2020 version of the International Geomagnetic Reference Field (IGRF) model to estimate the magnetic fields, and that the discrepancies noted between their estimates and those used in previous studies are likely attributable to the fact that the IGRF is updated every five years. Each update includes a *predictive* model for the next five years, as well as a *revised (definitive)* model for the preceding (and newly completed) five-year interval²⁵. In the latter case, measurements taken during the interval are used to adjust the model retrospectively. Estimating the magnetic field that exists in real time at a given location, as is done in magnetic displacement experiments, therefore invariably results in an IGRF estimate that will be modified slightly in the next iteration of the model.

Unlike Schneider et al. we consider it unlikely that a universal magnetic map exists in animals; instead, different species are likely to use different magnetic parameters in their maps

depending on what is useful where each lives^{1,13,20}. For example, magnetic declination (the difference between true north and magnetic north) might be useful to a bird in northern Europe, where declination varies strongly with longitude. Yet declination is useless to aquatic species that cannot clearly view the sky, a requirement for determining true north.

The emerging vision of magnetic maps is expansive, encompassing diverse strategies, the use of different magnetic parameters, and the recognition that natural selection is indifferent to whether a navigation system is perfect or fits human conceptions¹. The precision of a map is much less important than its utility to the organism. Natural selection will favor even a rough map if it enhances survival even slightly.

In sum, we agree that sensitivity is one factor that influences the specificity of an animal's magnetic map, but we find no basis for disparaging earlier work. Magnetic displacement is a robust technique for determining whether animals respond to regional magnetic fields; the possibility that animals might not interpret magnetic signatures as unique points should not stifle the creativity of navigation researchers. We encourage our fellow researchers to eschew assumptions regarding sensitivity, focus on strong experimental design, and simply let the animals show us what they can do.

Table 1. Inferred estimates of sensitivity to magnetic inclination angle.

Inferred sensitivity to magnetic inclination	Reference	Method and notes
~ 0.02 degrees	Wynn et al., 2020 ⁷	Changes in shearwater nesting locations were correlated with changes in inclination; of the birds that changed location, over half moved when inclination changed by as little as 0.01-0.02 degrees.
~ 0.04-0.05 degrees	Wynn et al., 2022 ⁸	Analyses provide evidence that reed warblers use specific (probably learned) inclination angles as a signal to terminate the return migration. See text for discussion.
~ 0.01-0.05 degrees	Rodda, 1984 ²⁶	Changes in homing orientation of alligators in relation to subtle changes in Earth's magnetic field

Table 2. Inferred estimates of sensitivity to magnetic intensity.

Inferred sensitivity to magnetic intensity	Reference	Method and notes
< 70 nT	Keeton et al., 1974 ²⁷	Deterioration of pigeon homing was correlated with slight geomagnetic disturbances; see also Gould, 1982 ¹⁶
< 20 nT	Dennis et al., 2007 ²⁸	Sensitivity inferred from an analysis of pigeon flight paths along intensity isolines after release in a magnetic anomaly
~40 nT	Southern, 1971 ²⁹	Disruption of orientation behavior in ring-billed gulls during slight geomagnetic disturbances
~30-60 nT	Putman et al., 2014 ¹²	Changes in migratory path of sockeye salmon were correlated with slight changes in Earth's magnetic field. The entire range of intensity differences for one multi-year data set only spans ~ 135 nT.
~20-40 nT	Putman et al., 2014 ¹²	Changes in migratory path of pink salmon correlated with slight changes in Earth's magnetic field. The entire range of intensity differences for a multi-year data set only spans ~ 69 nT
~26 nT	Walker and Bitterman, 1989 ³⁰	Best performance in honeybee conditioning study
~10 nT	Kirschvink and Gould, 1981 ³¹	Correlation between honeybee dance misdirection and slight changes in Earth's magnetic field

References

1. Lohmann, K. J., Goforth, K. M., Mackiewicz, A. G., Lim, D. S. & Lohmann, C. M. F. Magnetic maps in animal navigation. *J Comp Physiol A* **208**, 41–67 (2022).
2. Putman, N. F. *et al.* An inherited magnetic map guides ocean navigation in juvenile Pacific salmon. *Curr. Biol.* **24**, 446–450 (2014).
3. Lohmann, K. J., Cain, S. D., Dodge, S. A. & Lohmann, C. M. F. Regional magnetic fields as navigational markers for sea turtles. *Science* **294**, 364–366 (2001).
4. Chernetsov, N. *et al.* Migratory Eurasian reed warblers can use magnetic declination to solve the longitude problem. *Curr. Biol.* **27**, 2647–2651.e2 (2017).
5. Keller, B. A., Putman, N. F., Grubbs, R. D., Portnoy, D. S. & Murphy, T. P. Map-like use of Earth’s magnetic field in sharks. *Curr. Biol.* (2021) doi:10.1016/j.cub.2021.03.103.
6. Schneider, W. T., Packmor, F., Lindecke, O. & Holland, R. A. Sense of doubt: inaccurate and alternate locations of virtual magnetic displacements may give a distorted view of animal magnetoreception ability. *Communications Biology* **6**, 187 (2023).
7. Wynn, J., Padget, O., Mouritsen, H., Perrins, C. & Guilford, T. Natal imprinting to the Earth’s magnetic field in a pelagic seabird. *Curr. Biol.* **30**, 2869–2873.e2 (2020).
8. Wynn, J. *et al.* Magnetic stop sign signals a European songbird’s arrival at the breeding site after migration. *Science* **375**, 446–449 (2022).
9. Boles, L. C. & Lohmann, K. J. True navigation and magnetic maps in spiny lobsters. *Nature* **421**, 60–63 (2003).
10. Diego-Rasilla, F. J. & Phillips, J. B. Evidence for the use of a high-resolution magnetic map by a short-distance migrant, the Alpine newt (*Ichthyosaura alpestris*). *J Exp Biol* **224**, (2021).
11. Brothers, J. R. & Lohmann, K. J. Evidence for geomagnetic imprinting and magnetic navigation in the natal homing of sea turtles. *Curr. Biol.* **25**, 392–396 (2015).
12. Putman, N. F., Jenkins, E. S., Michielsens, C. G. J. & Noakes, D. L. G. Geomagnetic imprinting predicts spatio-temporal variation in homing migration of pink and sockeye salmon. *J. Royal Soc. Interface* **11**, 20140542–20140542 (2014).
13. Lohmann, K. J., Lohmann, C. M. F. & Putman, N. F. Magnetic maps in animals: nature’s GPS. *J. Exp. Biol.* **210**, 3697–3705 (2007).
14. Fuxjager, M. J., Eastwood, B. S. & Lohmann, K. J. Orientation of hatchling loggerhead sea turtles to regional magnetic fields along a transoceanic migratory pathway. *J. Exp. Biol.* **214**, 2504–2508 (2011).
15. Lohmann, K. J., Putman, N. F. & Lohmann, C. M. The magnetic map of hatchling loggerhead sea turtles. *Curr. Opin. Neurobiol.* **22**, 336–342 (2012).
16. Gould, J. L. The map sense of pigeons. *Nature* **296**, 205–211 (1982).
17. Lohmann, K. J. & Lohmann, C. M. F. Detection of magnetic field intensity by sea turtles. *Nature* **380**, 59–61 (1996).
18. Komolkin, A. V. *et al.* Theoretically possible spatial accuracy of geomagnetic maps used by migrating animals. *J. Royal Soc. Interface* **14**, 20161002 (2017)
19. Boström, J. E. *et al.* Autumn migratory fuelling: a response to simulated magnetic displacements in juvenile wheatears, *Oenanthe oenanthe*. *Behav Ecol Sociobiol* **64**, 1725–1732 (2010).

20. Putman, N. F., Endres, C. S., Lohmann, C. M. F. & Lohmann, K. J. Longitude perception and bicoordinate magnetic maps in sea turtles. *Curr. Biol.* **21**, 463–466 (2011).
21. Putman, N. F., Verley, P., Endres, C. S. & Lohmann, K. J. Magnetic navigation behavior and the oceanic ecology of young loggerhead sea turtles. *J. Exp. Biol.* **218**, 1044–1050 (2015).
22. Putman, N. F., Verley, P., Shay, T. J. & Lohmann, K. J. Simulating transoceanic migrations of young loggerhead sea turtles: merging magnetic navigation behavior with an ocean circulation model. *J. Exp. Biol.* **215**, 1863–1870 (2012).
23. Taylor, B. K. Bioinspired magnetoreception and navigation using magnetic signatures as waypoints. *Bioinspir. Biomim.* **13**, 046003 (2018).
24. Scanlan, M. M., Putman, N. F., Pollock, A. M. & Noakes, D. L. Magnetic map in nonanadromous Atlantic salmon. *PNAS* **115**, 10995–10999 (2018).
25. Alken, P., Thébaud, E., Beggan, C.D. *et al.* International Geomagnetic Reference Field: the thirteenth generation. *Earth Planets Space* **73**, 49 <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40623-020-01288-x> (2021).
26. Rodda, G. H. The orientation and navigation of juvenile alligators: evidence of magnetic sensitivity. *J. Comp. Physiol. A* **154**, 649–658 (1984).
27. Keeton, W. T., Larkin, T. S. & Windsor, D. M. Normal fluctuations in the earth's magnetic field influence pigeon orientation. *J. Comp. Physiol.* **95**, 95–103 (1974).
28. Dennis, T. E., Rayner, M. J. & Walker, M. M. Evidence that pigeons orient to geomagnetic intensity during homing. *Proc. R. Soc. B: Biol. Sci.* **274**, 1153–1158 (2007).
29. Southern, W. E. Gull orientation by magnetic cues: a hypothesis revisited. *Annals New York Acad. Sci.* **188**, 295–309 (1971).
30. Walker, M. M. & Bitterman, M. E. Honeybees can be trained to respond to very small changes in geomagnetic field intensity. *J. Exp. Biol.* **145**, 489–494 (1989).
31. Kirschvink, J. L. & Gould, J. L. Biogenic magnetite as a basis for magnetic field detection in animals. *Biosystems* **13**, 181–201 (1981).